

Fostering FAIR approaches to the seismological data life cycle

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Introduction

Natural disasters such as earthquakes floods and landslides expose communities living within hazard-prone areas to significant risks, particularly in today's increasingly interconnected world, making the need for advancement in multi-hazard assessment techniques critical. The HOMEROS project seeks to tackle the challenges presented by those advancements, focusing on seismology, geodesy and geology and leveraging cutting-edge technical solutions tailored to the big data era. HOMEROS makes strides in standardizing research methods, fostering collaboration, and improving the ability to understand and foresee natural hazards through Open Science practices. The project focuses on assessing hazard in high-risk areas in Greece, known for their significant seismic activity, major earthquake occurrence, floods, and landslides, through its transparent, reproducible and widely accessible research products. Data and tools developed by the project will strictly adhere to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), thereby maximizing their value for the scientific community, policy makers and stakeholders. HOMEROS will compile earthquake catalogues and assess ground deformation products to provide a comprehensive evaluation of seismic hazard. Furthermore, it will enhance knowledge of flood and landslide hazards, contributing to more effective mitigation efforts.

Project objectives

The HOMEROS project seeks to fulfill the critical need for reliable and standardized methods to assess multiple hazards in an increasingly dynamic risk environment. Harnessing the potential of Open Science and interdisciplinary collaboration, the project strives to expand scientific understanding, support data-informed decision-making, and strengthen community resilience. Its goals are centered around three core pillars:

- Utilization of platforms, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Environmental Research Infrastructure (ENVI) (Adamaki & Vermeulen, 2023) for the creation of accessible and efficient ecosystems for interdisciplinary data sharing. This effort builds on prior integration efforts in ENVI projects and promotes FAIR principles, ensuring usability and reproducibility of research outputs.
- Development of methodologies and workflows for integrating and utilising diverse datasets, including geodetic, seismic and geological data to create detailed physical models, visualization products, such as maps, and data inventories. These efforts seek to aid in the advancement and enhancement of multi-hazard assessment.
- Fostering collaboration and communication among research institutions, infrastructures, and projects. Scientific results will be shared through Open Access publications, workshops, and educational resources.

This paper presents data, workflows and results from the HOMEROS project, related to a specific swarm-like seismic excitation that occurred during the 2024 February – April period in the offshore area to the west of Asos village, Kefalonia island. This work includes preliminary findings from the project, highlighting the collaboration between the participating institutions and the potential for clear and reproducible scientific results by the adherence of available seismic datasets to FAIR principles.

Study area

The areas chosen as case studies for the HOMEROS project are the central Ionian Islands, along with the western Gulf of Corinth. These areas exhibit high deformation rates (Pikridas et al., 2016, Bitharis

et al., 2024), frequent occurrences of strong earthquakes (e.g., Papadimitriou et al., 2017; Kaviris et al., 2021; Sakkas et al., 2022) and destructive floods and landslides (Bathrellos et al., 2017, Skilodimou et al., 2018). More than 50% of the seismic energy in Europe is released in Greece, placing earthquakes among the most impactful geohazards in the country, highlighting the need for a reliable seismic hazard model. A comprehensive evaluation of seismic hazard for such areas can be achieved by Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) and Peak Ground Velocity (PGV) calculations, alongside site-specific analysis (Uniform Hazard Spectra – UHS and hazard curves) in towns that exhibit the highest population in the study areas (e.g., Kaviris et al., 2022, 2024).

The preliminary results presented in this paper concern the rigorous swarm taking place in 2024 in the offshore area west of Asos village of Kefalonia island. The study area is part of the Kefalonia Transform Fault Zone (KTFZ), which dominates the central Ionian Islands, which is the most seismically active area in the Mediterranean (Figure 1). Specifically, the swarm-like activity that lasted more than two months is located in a thoroughly studied part of the KTFZ, that is recognized as an extensional duplex transfer zone that links the northern (Lefkada) with the southern (Kefalonia) branches of the KTFZ (Karakostas et al., 2015). This stepover zone consists of small sub-parallel fault segments, striking roughly WSW–ENE, deflecting the azimuth of the main fault branches. Since only moderate magnitude earthquakes are known to have occurred in this area, this swarm-like excitation raises scientific concern for the exploitation of the large amount of seismological data that were collected during the activity and the exploitation of the collected data for deciphering the dynamic and kinematic properties of the activated structures. Advancing knowledge of the seismotectonic properties will provide valuable insight in assessing seismic hazard in the broader central Ionian Islands region.

Methods and data

High quality seismic data from regional networks are essential for the compilation of earthquake catalogue and the production of efficient data pipelines ready for multidisciplinary utilization. HOMEROS aims to exploit a benchmark seismic dataset for the February – April 2024 Central Ionian Islands swarm – like activity –among others–, containing more than 2000 earthquakes to explore integration opportunities for enhanced data exchange e.g., data pipelines between research groups of various disciplines, interested in leveraging seismic data for their research. This will be achieved by taking advantage of the resources provided by the EOSC and the ENVRI cluster. This effort also seeks to demonstrate the added value of these services, integrating their tools and services for multi-disciplinary research. Availability of both the relocated benchmark seismic catalogue and the raw waveform dataset will be enhanced following FAIR principles and Open Science practices, ensuring the ease of access to the data. To facilitate interoperability, the relocated catalogue will be provided in the QuakeML schema, a widely used form of seismological data representation, in a modular XML form, able to contain a variety of information, including moment tensors. The waveform dataset will be provided in miniSEED format, accompanied by the corresponding metadata for each station used to collect the data.

Along with providing ease of access to the benchmark data, HOMEROS aims to provide open-source tools for managing, obtaining, processing and visualizing seismic data. To this end, interactive coding platforms such as Jupyter Labs, will be utilized for better dissemination of the developed workflows and tools to scientists from different disciplines (e.g., in the form of Jupyter Notebooks), since an essential component of the project is to ensure the reproducibility, interoperability and ease of access of all research outputs of HOMEROS.

Figure 1: Map of the study area of the central Ionian islands. Circles and stars of different colors and sizes denote seismicity in the region since 1970, according to the legend. The area is placed within the context of the seismotectonics of the Aegean in the map inset, along with major structures of the region, marked with red lines. The main fault segments of the KTFZ, along with the extensional stepover area are denoted with red lines on the map of the study area. Arrows show the relative movement of the faults. The black rectangle encloses the region where the February – April 2024 seismic swarm took place, whereas the red rectangle denotes the location of Asos village

Exploitable results

The primary output for the seismology part of the HOMEROS project multi-hazard outputs, will be open-access datasets, including earthquake catalogues and waveform inventories. It is essential that these datasets will adhere to FAIR principles and be publicly available through platforms such as EPOS ERIC, ENVRI repositories, and other widely used repositories (e.g., GitHub, Zenodo). The benchmark seismic dataset for the February–April 2024 central Ionian Islands swarm-like activity contains over 2000 earthquakes with information on their relocated epicenters, depths, origin time, along with focal

mechanisms for a number of them (Figure 2). The waveform dataset of the swarm contains raw data along with station metadata for 14 seismic stations of the central Ionian Islands. Another key outcome is the development of clear and reproducible research workflows documented through interactive tools such as Jupyter Notebooks. These workflows will showcase the integration of seismic data with various datasets and methodologies, allowing researchers to replicate and tailor the processes for comparable studies, while also providing means of preliminary visualization of the data without the need of prior knowledge of complex tools developed for specific scientific disciplines. In our case, Jupyter notebooks containing complete workflows, along with instructions for waveform data homogenization and earthquake magnitude estimation will be provided.

Type	Description	Format
Raw data	Seismic Waveforms	miniSEED
Metadata	Station Metadata	StationXML (.xml)
Raw data	Earthquake Catalogues	QuakeML (.xml)
Raw data	Focal mechanisms	QuakeML (.xml)
Interactive notebook	Waveform dataset homogenization and Magnitude Estimation	Jupyter Notebook
Interactive notebook	Seismic data fetching and simple visualization	Jupyter Notebook

Table 1. Summary of expected data products for the February–April 2024 central Ionian Islands swarm-like activity case study of the HOMEROS project.

Figure 2: Relocated epicenters of earthquakes that occurred in the study area during the 24/02/2024 – 24/04/2024. Colored dots denote earthquakes with $0.1 \leq M \leq 3.7$, according to legend. The focal mechanisms of the 17 strongest earthquakes of the excitation are also presented, shown as equal area lower hemisphere projections. The excitation catalog, along with focal mechanisms, is currently available as a preliminary dataset (Anagnostou, 2025) and will be enhanced and finalized with clear metadata and reproducibility information, adhering to FAIR principles through the HOMEROS project.

A workflow along with instructions on obtaining seismic data from open access databases for specific temporal and spatial restrictions and visualizing them on simple maps (Figure 3) will be provided. These workflows will illustrate the combination of diverse datasets and methodologies, empowering researchers to replicate and modify the processes for related studies. Comprehensive documentation for each workflow, presented through interactive notebooks, will act as a best-practice reference for future multidisciplinary research endeavors.

Figure 3: Simple map created using the Seismic data fetching and visualization notebook, presenting earthquakes for the study area during the first 5 days of March 2024, when the excitation activity was peaking. Colored epicenters correspond to the magnitude color bar on the right side of the figure. Data obtained from public EMSC catalogues.

Conclusions

HOMEROS represents an important step forward in addressing the rapidly growing ramifications of multi-hazard assessment. Through unifying data from various scientific fields and embracing Open Science principles, the project addresses critical challenges in making hazard assessment thorough and accessible. By providing seismic datasets and developed workflows following FAIR principles, HOMEROS seeks to propel forward multidisciplinary collaboration and provide clear, reproducible scientific results. The project lays the foundation for scalable and interoperable tools and approaches to understanding natural hazards and their complex interactions. By focusing on a specific case study in a high-risk area such as the central Ionian Islands, we seek to demonstrate the practicality of our developed workflows, the accessibility of our seismic datasets and their potential for further utilization and application from researchers beyond the Earth sciences disciplines. Finally, the outputs comprising open-access data, scientific publications, and training modules, will provide valuable resources for policy-making and disaster management, contributing to a safer and more resilient society.

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